

EATING HABITS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. This thesis analyzes the relationship between human eating habits and their personal psychological characteristics. It is highlighted based on scientific sources that food choice behavior, eating time, quantity, and the need to eat are directly related to a person's character, emotional state, and stress level. Also, recommendations are given on the differences in eating between psychotypes, emotional eating states, and psychological health.

Keywords: eating habits, psychological characteristics, emotional eating, stress, personality types, healthy eating, psychological health.

Eating habits, which are an integral part of human life, are not only a biological need, but also an important factor related to psychological state and personal character. In recent years, research conducted at the intersection of psychology and nutrition sciences shows that what food people eat, when, and how much they eat largely depends on their internal experiences, mental state, and personality type.

Nutrition is the process of receiving and assimilating nutrients necessary for the normal functioning of the human body, maintaining health and working capacity. Proper and regular nutrition strengthens a person's immunity, reduces the likelihood of developing various diseases, and helps to more easily tolerate existing diseases. In addition, rational nutrition also plays an important role in preventing premature aging of the human body.

In some cases, in diseases of the cardiovascular system, gastrointestinal tract and other vital organs, a specially designed diet and special diets become an important component of the treatment process.

In order for food to ensure balanced development and continuous functioning of the body, it must correspond in quantity and quality to factors such as the age, gender, profession, and physical activity of the person. The physiological needs of the human body are constantly changing depending on external environmental conditions, internal conditions, and lifestyle. Therefore,

it is practically difficult to define a diet that is absolutely universal at all stages of life.

However, the body has special control mechanisms - regulatory systems - that separate and absorb nutrients from food. These systems ensure the selection and absorption of necessary substances depending on the current needs of the human body. However, these regulatory mechanisms are also limited. This flexibility is particularly weak in children and the elderly.

There are also some important nutrients that cannot be synthesized by the body, among which vitamins and essential amino acids occupy a special place. These substances must enter the human body in a ready state - through properly selected food. If these requirements are not taken into account and the diet is of poor quality, various diseases may occur.

That is, each person should establish a proper and balanced diet in accordance with their individual needs, consider it as a key factor in maintaining health and preventing various diseases. People's attitude towards food is closely related to their stress tolerance, level of anxiety, and mental stability. For example, some people have a decreased appetite during stress, while others tend to eat more. This condition is called "emotional eating" in psychology.

It is also worth noting that the Islamic religion pays great attention not only to a person's spiritual life, but also to his physical health. Like any living being, a person needs nutrition. If a person's soul is nourished through faith, righteous deeds, learning science, and reading books, then his body is nourished through halal and pure food and clean drinks. Therefore, in Islam, the issue of nutrition is viewed not just as a physical need, but as a spiritual and moral issue close to worship.

Moderation, halalness, and purity are the main principles of Islamic dietary guidelines. In the Holy Quran, Allah Almighty calls upon believers not to waste and to refrain from excessive consumption. This is important not only for economic reasons, but also from the point of view of maintaining health and ensuring social justice. Halalness in food consumption - that is, the use of products that Allah Almighty has permitted and declared pure - is an obligation for every Muslim.

Washing hands before and after eating is one of the Sunnah acts. In a hadith narrated by Salman, one of the companions of the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him), it is said: "The blessing of food is in washing before it and washing after it." This is not only hygienically beneficial, but also an important habit for spiritual purity and achieving the pleasure of Allah.

Another important etiquette is for respected people, i.e. people of knowledge and elders, to start the meal at the head of the table. When our Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) ate with us, the companions would not touch the food until he started. Hudhayfah (may Allah be pleased with him) said about this: “We used to eat with the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him), and none of us would touch the food until he started.”

In Islam, any good deed begins with saying “Bismillah” (in the name of Allah). Saying “Bismillah” before eating is starting this deed with the name of Allah and asking for His blessings. This is not only a Sunnah, but also an important remembrance that connects the heart to Allah.

Also, the Messenger of Allah (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) liked to start from the right side in every matter. Therefore, eating food with the right hand is a sunnah, and this practice is a follower of our Prophet. While eating, everyone should eat the food in front of them and not reach out to someone else. This etiquette is a sign of respect and order. Reaching out to food in front of others is considered rude.

These eating etiquette are not just external culture, but acts of worship that bring a Muslim closer to Allah through every daily action. Therefore, these etiquettes must be taught to children from a young age and maintained in families and society. Unfortunately, these values are being forgotten in some societies. On the contrary, we are trying to preserve them, pass them on from generation to generation, and perpetuate them.

Psychological types (introvert-extrovert, neurotic, emotional, disciplined, etc.) make a significant difference in food choices and eating habits:

- Extroverts - often tend to eat in a group, try new dishes.
- Introverts - prefer familiar, safe foods, enjoy eating alone.
- Impulsive individuals - tend to eat quickly without thinking.
- Highly anxious individuals - often strive for diets, but this may not last long.

In addition, one of the main rules of modern medicine and a healthy lifestyle is to eat in an amount that corresponds to the daily energy needs of the human body. Insufficient intake of calories or, conversely, excessive consumption of calories can lead to serious health problems. For example, due to a calorie deficit, a person experiences general weakness, decreased activity, and weight loss. On the contrary, overeating leads to obesity and can cause dangerous diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and hypertension.

Therefore, diet plays an important role in food culture. Diet is not just a restriction, but also the timing, quantity, composition, and proper distribution of calories in each meal. Experts recommend that healthy people eat three to four times a day. Each meal should last at least 30 minutes, as this is important for the body to fully digest food and get the most out of it.

Food culture serves not only to maintain health, but also reflects aesthetic education and the cultural level of society. The compatibility of food products with each other, their digestion in the body, enjoyment of food, the art of preparing and decorating food are also part of this culture. This culture is expressed not only in the home, but also at official events and celebrations.

Eating at formal banquets and receptions is different from ordinary everyday meals. It requires a certain order and culture from the participants. In particular, the aesthetic decoration of the table, the arrangement of dishes, cutlery, glasses and wine glasses, and the correct order of their use are important. The sequence of eating is important, first salads and snacks should be served, then main (hot) dishes, and finally desserts and fruits.

At formal events, food serves not only to nourish the body, but also to fulfill a certain social function, namely, communication, negotiation, and exchange of ideas between guests. Therefore, in such cases, enjoying the food is secondary, and the important aspect is to act in accordance with the culture of the event.

Drinks also require special attention. For example, cocktails should be served in special glasses, and coffee in cups. Desserts and fruits can be served in aesthetically pleasing dishes - wooden plates or disposable plastic cups. At the same time, mini forks or spoons should be provided for the convenience of guests.

It is polite to start eating at banquets only after the host invites you. Guests patiently take turns eating, starting with the first snacks. This is not only a sign of social etiquette, but also a sign of organizational order and respect.

Therefore, the development of a food culture is not only learning the rules of eating, but also one of the important steps taken towards maintaining health, cultivating aesthetic taste, and forming social culture. Every intelligent person should deeply understand this culture and make it an integral part of their life.

In many cases, people overeat in situations such as loneliness, sadness, boredom, and anxiety. Such eating indicates that psychological needs (love, attention, security) are not satisfied. Situations of controlling emotions through food have a negative impact on health in the long term.

Eating psychology is a field of psychology aimed at studying the emotional states, thoughts, and behaviors of people during the eating process, and it analyzes psychological factors in eating. This field covers topics such as how to control appetite, change eating habits, and the impact of eating on mental health.

The psychology of eating covers the following areas:

Psychological effects of eating: It studies what feelings and thoughts a person has when eating, and how food affects their mental state.

Appetite management: It analyzes the possibilities of increasing or decreasing appetite through eating, and also studies the influence of the psychological environment on appetite.

Changes in eating habits: It focuses on analyzing how eating speed, eating duration, and other behaviors change.

Nutritional psychology plays an important role in working with the following groups:

Working with students: Conducts educational activities aimed at developing healthy eating, appetite control, and healthy eating habits among them.

Working with children: It is important to teach children the impact of nutrition on their mental state, as well as healthy eating habits from an early age.

Working with family and loved ones: Informing family members about the psychological aspects of nutrition and helping them change their daily eating habits in a positive way are among the tasks of this field.

In general, the psychology of eating is a relevant scientific direction that includes an in-depth analysis of people's internal experiences, thought processes, and behaviors during eating.

Healthy eating provides not only physical, but also psychological health. Healthy eating habits strengthen self-control, stress management, and discipline in a person. Therefore, nutrition psychology is considered an integral part of a healthy lifestyle.¹

Conclusion, A person's eating habits and psychological state have a strong influence on each other. Forming a diet in accordance with psychological characteristics is an important factor in strengthening health and maintaining mental balance. In this direction, the cooperation of psychologists and nutritionists is becoming an integral part of a modern healthy lifestyle.

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